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Research Article

Improvement Of The Product Robustness Of Allopurinol With Minor Changes

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research work is to improve the robustness of allopurinol with minor changes. These studies aimed to develop a allopurinol tablet formulation by wet granulation method. The studies of the tablets are pre-compression parameters like angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, and Hausner ratio, and post compression parameters like appearance, thickness, hardness test, friability test, weight variation test, disintegration test, and stability studies. Finally, all parameters are within the limit. Allopurinol tablets containing higher concentration of povidone K-30 appears to be the best formulation. Hence, it may be summarized that the tablets prepared by wet granulation method might be a perfect and effective formulation to prevent the treatment of gout.

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INTRODUCTION

Allopurinol (1,5-Dihydro-4H-pyrazolo (3, 4-d) pyrimidin-4-one) is structural isomer of hypoxanthine which is xanthine oxidase inhibitor, commonly used in the treatment of chronic gout associated with pathological conditions like leukemia, inflammation and in cancer medications. The drug is particularly useful in patients with recurrent renal deposition of urates, proliferative disease and malignancies [1-8]. The aim of this research work is to improve the robustness of allopurinol with minor changes. These studies aimed to develop allopurinol tablet formulation by wet granulation method. A total of 4 formulations using various concentration of povidone K-30.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Evaluation of the pharmaceutical powders

Bulk density determination

Weighed quantity of the powder (W) was taken in a graduated measuring cylinder and volume (V₀) was measured and bulk density was calculated using the formula.

Bulk density (BD)= Weight of the powder/ Volume of powder

$$BD = W/V_0 \text{ g/mL}$$

Tapped density determination

Weighed quantity of powder was taken in a graduated cylinder and the volume was measured (V₀). The graduated cylinder was fixed in the 'Tapped Densimeter' and tapped for 500, 750 and 1250 times until the difference in the volume after consecutive tappings was less than 2%. The final reading was denoted by (V_f).

$$\text{Tapped density(TD)}= W_g/m_l$$

Angle of repose

Angle of Repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of the powder and the horizontal plane.

Table 1: Angle of repose and corresponding flow properties

Angle of repose	Flow property
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very Poor

Carr's index:

Carr's index is also known as compressibility. It is indirectly related to the relative flow rate,

cohesiveness and particle size. It is simple, fast and popular method of predicting powder flow characteristics.

Table 2: Carr's index and corresponding flow properties

Carr's Index(%)	Flow property
5-15	Excellent
16-18	Good
18-21	Fair to Passable
23-35	Poor
33-38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

Hausner ratio

Hausner ratio indicates the flow properties of the powder and measured by the ratio of tapped density to bulk density. The relationship between Hauser's ratio and flow property (9-12).

Table 3: Hausner ratio and corresponding flow properties

Hausner Ratio	Property
0-1.2	Free flowing
1.2-1.6	Cohesive Powder

Assay

This test is a quantitative version of the identification test. Again, 10–20 tablets are ground and the active ingredient is dissolved or extracted in a suitable solvent using the standard procedure. The concentration of the extracted solution is determined using a specific and validated

spectroscopic or chromatographic method against a solution of reference standard. These results are reported as percent of expected/labeled value. Uniformity of dosage unit, friability, hardness testing, disintegration test, dissolution were carried out using standard procedure and apparatus/ instrument (13-18).

Table 4: Formulation and Development of Core tablets

Sr. No	Ingredients	Formulation Code (mg)			
		F1	F2	F3	F4
01	Allopurinol	100	100	100	100
02	Lactose Monohydrate	170	170	150	140
03	Maize Starch	25	25	40	37
04	Povidone (K – 30)	03	03	05	10
05	Stearic Acid	02	02	05	05
06	Maize Starch	-	-	-	8
07	Purified Water		q.s.	q.s.	q.s.

RESULTS**Pre - compression Parameters**

Evaluation of Pre-compression and Post-compression parameters of allopurinol tablets

Table 5: Pre-compression parameters of allopurinol tablets

Formulation	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4
Bulk density(g/ml)	0.61	0.590	0.62	0.590
Tapped density(g/ml)	0.77	0.632	0.75	0.615
Carr's index	20.7	6.64	17.33	4.06
Hausner Ratio (HR)	1.26	1.07	1.20	1.04

Post- compression Parameters**Table 6: Post compression parameters**

Parameters	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4
Average weight /tablet	300.2	300.6	299.7	299.5
Thickness	4.0	3.9	4.1	3.8
Hardness	3.0-4.0	4.5-6.0	4.0-5.5	4.3-5.6
Friability	0.12	0.18	0.13	0.16
Disintegration time	2.10	2.55	2.60	2.35

Hardness

The hardness of six tablets of each batch was checked by using Pfizer hardness tester The result

showed that the hardness of the tablets was in the range of 3.0 to 5.6kg/cm²

Thickness

Thickness of the six tablets of each batch was measured by using Vernier Calipers. The results showed that the thickness of the tablets was in the range of 3.8 to 4.1mm respectively.

Weight variation test

Tablets of each batch were subjected to weight variation test, difference in weight and percent deviation was calculated for each tablet.

Friability

Tablets of each batch were evaluated for percentage friability. The average friability of all the formulations lies in the range of 0.12 to 0.18 % which was less than 1% as per official requirement

of IP indicating a good mechanical resistance of tablets.

Invitro disintegration time

Tablets of each batch were evaluated for in-vitro disintegration time. The results showed that the disintegration time of prepared tablets were in the range of 2.10 to 2.55 mins.

Invitro dissolution studies

The in-vitro dissolution studies were conducted in phosphate buffer pH 0.01N HCL. The Formulation F4 contains showed 98.15% of drug release within 45min.

DISSOLUTION PROFILE

Table 7: Dissolution profile

TIME	Trial-1	Trial-2	Trial-3	Trial-4
10 mins	5	8	12	15
15 mins	35	39	42	45
20 mins	53	59	66	70
30 mins	69	73	77	80
45 mins	76	82	90	98

Fig 1 : Dissolution profile

CONCLUSION

The improvement robustness of this product allopurinol 300mg was successfully formulated. Systemic formulation development was proceeded with exhaustive drug excipient compatibility study to finalize the excipient. Allopurinol tablets

containing higher concentration of povidone K-30 appears to be the best formulation. The Pre-compression parameters of all formulations showed good flow properties and these can be used for tablet manufacture. The post compression parameters of all formulations were determined

and the values were found to be within the pharmacopoeial limits. Wet granulation method is the best-suited method for formulating of allopurinol tablets. Thus it may be concluded that the development of allopurinol can be successfully prepared and evaluated and its popularity in the future.

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